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"Investigating Code-Switching as a Tool for English Language Education: Student Views and Outcomes"

Melencio, Ashllie Krisna A., Dado, Susana D., Manuel, Mary Grace A., Alba, Rodelio M.

ABSTRACT

This study examines how students view and interact with code-switching, a technique used in English language classes to switch from English to a vernacular language, such as Filipino or Tagalog. Drawing on a sociolinguistic lens incorporating translanguaging and communication accommodation theories, a mixed-methods design was used to explore student attitudes and outcomes. Findings revealed that many students felt more self-assured when participating in English discussions after code-switching, particularly during grammar instruction and oral activities. However, some students expressed continued hesitation about using English exclusively. These insights suggest that code-switching can be a beneficial instructional method when applied intentionally. Still, educators must strike a balance to avoid students becoming too reliant on their native language. Ultimately, the study calls for culturally responsive teaching strategies that reflect learners' linguistic realities and promote inclusive learning environments.

Keywords: code-switching, translanguaging, second language acquisition, language acquisition, student attitudes, bilingual education, sociolinguistics

INTRODUCTION

Code-switching is a significant component of learning a second language, particularly in multilingual communities where individuals adeptly blend and switch between various languages (Wirhayati & Safitri, 2020). Switching between two or more languages during a single conversation or discourse has piqued the interest of linguists, sociolinguists, and educators (Sajib et al., 2020). Code-switching has become more common and important because of globalization and online communication channels that make people more connected (Caparaz & Gustilo, 2017).

In classrooms, code-switching is a dynamic and complex way for students and teachers to talk to each other. It affects how teachers and students interact with each other and how they think about language learning. To fully understand the complicated dynamics of code-switching, we need to look at its sociolinguistic roots, cognitive effects, and teaching effects, especially when learning English. Code-switching is deeply rooted in society and depends a lot on the situation in which it happens. It connects language, identity, and social relationships (Caparaz & Gustilo, 2017). Teachers and students use it to help them talk to each other and fill in language gaps in formal and informal learning

settings (Ezeh et al., 2022). Although opinions on the effectiveness of code-switching in the classroom vary greatly, it is crucial to have a solid grasp of students' thought processes and experiences to assess this practice's impact (Rustiyani, 2020).

The Importance of Code-Switching in Language Learning

Code-switching can be an effective teaching strategy if the objective is to enhance language instruction (Almagableh & Yunus, 2022). Instructors can employ code-switching to improve comprehension, maintain students' interest, and foster mutual trust (Bhatti et al., 2018). It is a good way to pass on knowledge by using parts of known languages, like words, sentences, or phrases, that learners can understand (Mawela & Mahlambi, 2021). Teachers often switch languages to make things easier to understand and to help students interact more easily in class. Students can respond more easily without having to think too hard about how to understand complex English sentences. Also, students' code-switching can show their confidence, especially when they risk being linguistically vulnerable (Mauliddiyah et al., 2020).

Most learners use code-switching to deal with communication gaps, clear up confusion, and share complex ideas that are hard to put into words

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in the target language alone (Almagableh & Yunus, 2022). However, its success depends on many things, like how good the students are at the language, what the teacher wants to teach, and the classroom's overall social and linguistic environment. There are, however, some limits to code-switching.

It can be used to show that someone depends on their first language because they do not get enough instruction in English, making it harder to speak and write fluently and accurately in the target language (Nurhamidah et al., 2018). Using code-switching too much or without control can confuse things, slow learning target-language skills, and reinforce incorrect grammatical patterns (Afriani, 2020). This dualism demonstrates the need for additional empirical studies examining the benefits and drawbacks of code-switching in language learning from the learner's perspective. Kamal and Ramly (2022) say that code-switching can be a good way to improve English teaching and learning, especially regarding online learning. Additionally, it promises to create more inclusive and culturally sensitive classrooms where students feel comfortable expressing themselves (Herawati & Fitriani, 2021).

This study explores students' perceptions and experiences of code-switching in English language learning. Specifically, it investigates whether code-switching is a supportive or hindering strategy in developing comprehension, communicative competence, and motivation, considering cognitive, social, and affective dimensions (Toribio, 2002). Specifically, it answers the following questions:

- How does code-switching impact students' understanding of English language materials?
- What are the potential benefits and difficulties in enhancing students' English language proficiency and fluency?
- How does code-switching affect students' attitudes, confidence, and motivation for learning English?

Code-switching does not significantly impact students' comprehension, communicative competence, or affective engagement (motivation, confidence, and attitude) in English language learning.

Using theories of language contact, bilingualism, and identity, this study examines code-switching in English language classrooms from a sociolinguistic perspective. It includes the idea of translanguaging, which says that code-switching is more than just switching between languages. It is a purposeful, dynamic, and natural process that

multilingual speakers use to make meaning, make sure they understand, and show who they are (Hopewell & Abril-Gonzalez, 2019; Tai, 2021). The translanguaging approach differs from traditional models that treat languages as separate systems. It assumes multilinguals flexibly use a single linguistic repertoire based on their communication and cognitive needs. At the classroom level, this lets students work with academic material, communicate subtle meaning, and build confidence, especially when doing complex or high-stakes tasks like reporting or discussion.

The study also uses Communication Accommodation Theory (CAT), which explains how people change how they talk to fit in with others. For example, code-switching can be used to show whether people are getting along or not (Shahida & Shoukat, 2021). School students can switch between English and their first language to connect with peers or teachers, ease their nerves, or control how they present themselves. This theory explains why some students are more comfortable with code-switching than others. Some students use it to become fluent and understand, while others resist it because they think they should or are afraid of punishment.

Together, these theories provide a rich analytical framework for examining how code-switching functions in students' everyday lives, boosting self-esteem, facilitating grammatical comprehension, and displaying agency and constraint in language learning environments. Thus, integrating sociolinguistics, translanguaging, and CAT supports a sophisticated understanding of how identity, context, and interpersonal communication shape language practices.

The conceptual framework of this study is based on students' opinions about code-switching, their experiences with it in the classroom, their attitudes toward the practice, and the effects of code-switching on their English language learning outcomes. Teaching style, classroom culture, peer interaction, and academic expectations are some of the factors that influence these perceptions and experiences. These constructs are considered in the

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larger educational, cultural, and social context in which students operate.

Whether students view code-switching as beneficial, necessary, or restrictive, their perceptions reflect how they interpret and give meaning to its use in English instruction. Students' actual experiences practicing code-switching, particularly during class activities like recitation, reporting, or discussion. Students' emotional and value reactions—whether favorable, ambivalent, or unfavorable—to the simultaneous use of both languages are referred to as attitudes. The three elements influence learning outcomes like improved comprehension, increased confidence, a greater appreciation of grammar, or a persistent hesitancy to use English to its fullest. The model acknowledges the context-specificity of these interactions. For instance, students are more likely to feel empowered to use their native tongue strategically in classrooms that encourage translanguaging. However, students are likely to internalize fear or apprehension of judgment in environments that support English-only policies, affecting their willingness to participate. The framework also encourages a two-way effect, whereby students' experiences and accomplishments can eventually reshape their attitudes and perspectives. The framework generally views code-switching as a sociocultural and pedagogical practice based on the dynamics of identity, learning, and interpersonal communication rather than as an isolated linguistic phenomenon. It promotes the study's objective to examine the intricacy of language learning using students' real-life experiences as they transition between languages to become proficient, self-assured, and academically successful.

Literature Review on Code-Switching and Language Acquisition

Code-switching has been extensively studied from a cross-linguistic and cross-societal perspective, which is defined as the seamless transition between two or more languages during a single communicative event. The multilateral nature of code-switching and its intricate relationship with linguistic proficiency, social identity, and communication strategy have been clarified by earlier research. According to research, code-switching serves various pragmatic functions, including negotiating social identities, emphasizing points, and providing clarification (Yim & Clément, 2021). Code-switching is used to switch between Arabic and English and is considered an ideal social practice (Algharabali et al., 2015). It has been suggested that speakers use code-switching to draw

in the audience and show that they understand the terms used in the discussion (Akeel, 2016). Code-switching is common among bilingual and multilingual learners in academic settings, particularly in language classes where students can use their linguistic repertoire to manage complex learning tasks, facilitate communication, and improve understanding (Brice, 2000).

Additionally, research has examined the cognitive effects of code-switching, examining potential effects on memory, attention, and language processing. Some studies contend that code-switching can promote cognitive flexibility and metalinguistic consciousness, while others support the idea that it can put learners under more cognitive strain. According to Hamdan (2023), code-switching can be used for various communicative purposes, including emotional expression, discourse marking, referential purposes, and clarification.

Researchers continue to debate whether code-switching has a facilitatory or inhibitory effect on language acquisition. According to some academics, code-switching can be a proper scaffolding technique that aids learners in connecting new language concepts with their existing language knowledge (Fithriani, 2021). However, other research cautions against using code-switching excessively or inappropriately, citing its potential to impede the acquisition of proper linguistic structures and delay the development of target language proficiency. The pedagogical success of code-switching will depend on several factors, including the learners' level of proficiency, the type of learning task, and the teacher's capacity to use code-switching sparingly as part of instructional practice. Furthermore, the sociolinguistic context in which code-switching is employed likely influences how it impacts language acquisition. Additionally, it is used to reassert a sense of community and to communicate a sense of agency over one's social identity (Falbo & LaCroix, 2021). Teachers' attitudes toward code-switching can greatly influence students' perceptions and experiences; some may discourage its use in the classroom, while others may view it as a legitimate pedagogical technique (Treffers-Daller et al., 2022).

In schools, code-switching is a complex interplay between linguistic policies, instructional strategies, and student experiences that affect language acquisition in several ways. The decision of whether to permit or prohibit code-switching in multilingual classrooms is a common one for teachers, who must weigh the advantages of the practice against the risks to target language development. Switching between languages can

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facilitate communication and enhance understanding, particularly when students encounter new or unfamiliar language or structure. Teachers who promote code-switching in the classroom help students engage in translanguaging, encompassing their full linguistic repertoire. Students can use their entire linguistic repertoire to mediate meaning and interact more effectively with learning materials by code-switching (Zainil & Arsyad, 2021). According to Chen and Rubinstein-Ávila (2015), code-switching may foster a more welcoming and encouraging learning atmosphere where students feel comfortable expressing themselves and experimenting with their language acquisition process. According to empirical research, code-switching can help students become more metalinguistically aware, which helps them examine the parallels and discrepancies between their languages and improve their comprehension of linguistic ideas.

By comparing and contrasting linguistic features across languages, students can enhance their analytical and interpretative skills of linguistic data and improve their comprehension of the basic structure of language. Code-switching can be a proper scaffolding strategy that lets teachers give students focused guidance and support as they complete complex learning tasks. Teachers can strategically employ code-switching to give feedback, give additional examples, and assist students in understanding complex concepts. However, classroom code-switching must be closely watched to prevent any adverse effects. Some educators worry that excessive or unnecessary code-switching may hinder students' progress toward mastering the target language, causing errors to become fossilized and preventing them from achieving accuracy and fluency.

Additionally, some people believe that code-switching is linked to linguistic incompetence (Roslan et al., 2021). To reduce these risks, educators must set strict guidelines and expectations for code-switching in the classroom and encourage students to use it effectively.

Understanding students' attitudes toward and experiences with code-switching is essential to creating effective and supportive language learning environments. Students' feelings about code-switching vary depending on their cultural identity, linguistic background, and prior language learning experiences. While some students may find code-switching to be a helpful tool that helps them communicate more effectively and get through challenging assignments, others may be shy or hesitant to use it in the classroom out of fear of social

stigmatization or unfavorable evaluations from peers and teachers. Some students may view code-switching as a sign of linguistic weakness or a barrier to achieving native-like proficiency in the target language. Students' perceptions of code-switching will also be influenced by the attitudes of their teachers and peers. In a friendly and supportive classroom setting where code-switching is recognized as a sincere and acceptable mode of communication, students can grow to feel like they belong and learn to embrace their linguistic diversity. However, a controlling or stigmatizing environment where code-switching is discouraged or devalued can cause students to feel anxious and insecure, hindering their language learning process. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that students frequently use code-switching and code-mixing (Humaera et al., 2018). Additionally, students can use code-switching to negotiate power dynamics in the classroom, express their identities, and show solidarity with their peers.

Teachers can create more culturally and linguistically sensitive teaching strategies that support students' motivation, engagement, and success by learning about their experiences and perceptions. Teachers' code-mixing behaviors can also serve educational goals, such as promoting learning and bilingualism (Jiang et al., 2014). In multilingual environments, code-switching is frequent (Sitaram et al., 2019). Language proficiency, social context, and individual identity all impact this complex phenomenon (Deuchar, 2020; Mabule, 2015). Changing codes could be done for various reasons, including managing power dynamics, indicating solidarity, or facilitating communication (Nurhayati, 2021). According to proficiency in the languages being used, code-switching involves varying degrees of switching or blending (Mabule, 2015). It is crucial to comprehend the dynamics of code-switching in diverse social and educational contexts (AIRumaihi, 2021; Brice, 2000; Gardner-Chloros, 2009; Krasas, 2018). Both intrasentential (within sentences) and intersentential (between sentences) code-switching takes place (Sahib et al., 2021). At certain syntactic boundaries, speakers transition between languages intrasententially (Sankoff, 1998). Code-switching is more common among speakers who want to convey a common identity and are relatively balanced regarding socioeconomic status and bilingualism (Alasmari, 2021). It is common in literature, social media, and television (Andani et al., 2022). Speakers' identities impact their chosen language (Devikasari & Markhamah, 2023).

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Examining the code-switching experiences of English language learners yields valuable insights into the dynamics of multilingual language acquisition and identity negotiation. English language learners may employ code-switching as a daily coping mechanism to lessen the strain of speaking a foreign language, particularly when confronted with unfamiliar grammar or vocabulary. Furthermore, code-switching allows students to use their existing linguistic resources and cultural knowledge to improve understanding and participation in class activities (Gamotin, 2021). EFL learners typically use code-switching for various reasons influenced by their roles, relationships, interactions, and topics of choice (Masna, 2020).

English language learners' experiences with code-switching are impacted by their differences in personality, attitudes, and values, as well as by their level of English proficiency, attitudes toward their native tongue, and the attitudes of their teachers and peers. Some students will be hesitant to switch codes out of concern that they will be perceived as less proficient in English or that others will think poorly of them. To lower these risks, teachers need to make the classroom a safe and welcoming place where students can use all of their language skills and code-switching is seen as a valid way to communicate.

Code-switching behavior can reveal information about the cognitive processes that underlie language acquisition and how language is used and developed. Learners' strengths and shortcomings in a variety of linguistic competence domains, such as their preferred methods for communicating meaning and handling social situations, can be determined by code-switching patterns (Ilmassafa et al., 2023). Additionally, analyzing code-switching patterns can help teachers identify areas where students might need more help or direction and organize their teaching methods to meet their students' varied needs better. Due to the interaction of teachers who support and facilitate students by code-switching in certain situations, code-switching has been effective in classrooms (Mauliddiyah et al., 2020).

Also, code-switching can help people learn second languages in many ways, such as by helping them understand, speak, and be aware of language itself (Rustiyani, 2020). Students may use code-switching, for example, to demonstrate their comprehension of a concept, practice new vocabulary or grammar rules, or reflect on the parallels and discrepancies between their languages. Students are assumed to use code-switching to perform various discourse functions,

such as topic switching, interjection, repetition, elaboration, and personalization. In order to manage it and have access to the language, students also utilize code-switching in the classroom (Almagableh & Yunus, 2022). Code-switching is another helpful way to get students to participate in class. Under the Department of Education's Bilingual Education Policy, English is one of the languages that can be used as the medium of instruction (Enriquez et al., 2022). Because they employ code-switching, the students can readily understand what the teacher describes when given a lesson (Hamid, 2016). Because they understand the lesson well, the students can readily learn more about it.

Additionally, research shows that code-switching can help language learners understand, communicate, and learn the language (Beatty-Martínez et al., 2020). The effectiveness of code-switching as a learning strategy can depend on the situation in which it is used, the students' level of proficiency, and how their peers and teachers feel about it (Ulfah et al., 2021). For example, students can use code-switching to show how they feel and are part of a group, and clarify things. Teachers usually switch between the local language and English, and students usually switch between English and the local language (Ulfah et al., 2021). Teachers can make classrooms more welcoming and inclusive by encouraging code-switching (Hammond, 2020).

Research Gap

Few studies have been conducted on students' experiences and perceptions of code-switching, particularly among English language learners, even though there has been an increase in interest in this practice in educational settings. The majority of the research that is currently available tends to ignore the crucial impact that students' subjective experiences have on learning in favor of concentrating on what teachers believe or the linguistic characteristics of code-switching (Bahous et al., 2013; Sastra & Adriyanti, 2022). How code-switching affects learning English, especially how students think and feel, fills a gap in the research. This study also fills this gap by determining what English language learners think about code-switching through a qualitative approach.

The study examines how English language learners understand code-switching in their classrooms. It wants to know how students feel about code-switching, how it affects their education, and what shapes their opinions. This study closes the gap by giving English language learners a voice and a deeper understanding of their experiences and

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views on code-switching. The results will give teachers and policymakers specific information on how to use code-switching to help English language learners (Eldin, 2014; Panhwar, 2018; Wang, 2017) improve their language and academic skills.

METHODOLOGY

Using a mixed-methods design, this study investigated the impact of switching codes between English and Filipino on students' English language proficiency. It focused on the students' self-reported vocabulary, grammar, speaking, and listening improvements. By integrating quantitative and qualitative data, the mixed-methods design allowed for a deeper comprehension of the phenomenon and improved the interpretation of the findings (Ayana et al., 2024; Kuschel et al., 2023).

Students' perceptions of their language development regarding code-switching were quantified using Likert-scale questionnaires. Open-ended questions and interviews were used to gather qualitative data, which looked at students' daily experiences and personal perceptions of code-switching. This methodological design was based on a qualitative descriptive framework, which made it possible to get a deep, rich understanding of the phenomenon and a close look at code-switching in the context of language acquisition (Azis & Rahmawati, 2021; Maryansyah et al., 2024).

Qualitative and quantitative techniques are utilized to obtain an array of different kinds of data (Youssef, 2017). The researcher used a questionnaire with ten Likert-scale items and a few open-ended questions made for the study to find out how the students felt. This combination made it possible to get both measurable data and direct accounts of what students thought about code-switching and how it was said to affect learning (Babanto et al., 2023).

Students' degrees of agreement regarding how code-switching impacted their English vocabulary, grammar, speaking, and listening development were gauged by the Likert-scale questions. Conversely, open-ended questions prompted students to offer more complex ideas. Semi-structured interviews with some students were used to add more depth to the data. These interviews allowed the students to describe their experiences, benefits, and drawbacks of code-switching (Muthusamy et al., 2020). Additionally, focus group interviews provided a collaborative platform for students to elaborate on their perspectives, introducing a wider range of shared opinions.

Descriptive statistics were used to determine the quantitative data and summarize what students said about Likert-scale items. We used the Kruskal-Wallis H test to see if students' opinions on how code-switching affected them were statistically different between the different class groups. The non-parametric test was appropriate because the data only included average English grades for each class and ordinal-level Likert-scale scores, not individual student grades. The Kruskal-Wallis H test could be used to compare more than two independent groups to see any significant differences in the distributions of their perception scores (Calver & Fletcher, 2020; Clark et al., 2023). Using this method, the researcher could compare the class average in English performance to the self-assessed improvement in English competence.

The qualitative data included open-ended questions and interviews with students. Thematic analysis was used to find common themes and patterns in their answers. It added to the survey results from quantitative data and gave us a better idea of how students felt about and understood using code-switching in their learning. Combining the two analysis techniques made triangulation of results possible, providing richer, contextual student narratives to support survey conclusions.

To make sure the research tools were valid and reliable, the interview protocols and questionnaire were based on proven theoretical models and related literature (Shengyao et al., 2024). We pilot-tested the questionnaire and made changes as needed to make it more straightforward and ensure the items accurately reflected the measured constructs. We used test-retest reliability to see how stable the instrument was over time, and we used Cronbach's alpha to see how consistent the Likert-scale items were with each other (Hussain & Turki Hussain, 2025). Triangulation, which compares evidence from multiple sources (open-ended questions, interviews, and focus groups) to ensure that results are consistent and reliable, enhanced the credibility of the qualitative data. Several data collection techniques helped to confirm key themes and reduce bias in interpretation.

The experiment was conducted in the junior high school department of St. Joseph College, a bilingual institution offering Filipino and English academic instruction. This natural environment provided the ideal setting for observing the effects of code-switching in real-world learning settings. The school's bilingual curriculum and diverse student body made a more thorough analysis of how students switched between languages during instruction and how this impacted language

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development possible (Enriquez et al., 2022; Gardner-Chloros, 2009).

Convenience sampling was used to select the respondents, who were students from four sections. Convenience sampling was chosen because it was easy to conduct the study within pre-existing class schedules, and the participants were easily accessible. Grades 7 and 8 students who experienced code-switching in their English classes made up the population (Masna, 2020; Desoyo, 2021). Because of their varied learning experiences and levels of English language proficiency, they were sampled, expanding the size of the data set.

The study followed all ethical rules (Tam et al., 2020). Before the study began, the participants and their guardians agreed to participate. They were told what the study was about, that they could stop participating without any problems, and that keeping their answers to themselves was important. All reports and analyses used anonymized participant identities. In order to maintain objectivity and avoid conflicts of interest, the researchers collected and interpreted the data in an unbiased manner. Data management and reporting openness also preserved the research's ethical legitimacy (Valieva et al., 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1. Perception of Self-Confidence and Average English Grade

Participants	Likert Scale Question		Average English Grade	
	Average Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	No Code Switching	With Code Switching
Class 1	3.57	Confident	90	93
Class 2	3.48	Confident	89	93
Class 3	3.66	Confident	91	95
Class 4	3.41	Confident	85	88

Table 1 shows how students felt about their ability to use English in class and their average English grades, both with and without code-switching. The Likert scale's Average Weighted Mean (AWM) scores, which ranged from 3.41 to 3.66, fell into the "Confident" category for each of the four classes. Additionally, class averages increased by 2 to 4 points compared to when code-switching was not used, indicating a significant improvement in English grades.

Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to see if the differences in self-confidence and English grades between the four classes were statistically significant. Here are the results:

Table 2. Kruskal-Wallis H Test Results

Group	H Statistic	p-value	Significant ($\alpha = 0.05$)
Perceived Self-Confidence (AWM)	19.00	0.000273	Yes
English Grades (With Code-Switching)	19.00	0.000273	Yes

The test showed a statistically significant difference between the four classes regarding English grades in code-switching ($H = 19.00$, $p = 0.000273$) and perceived self-confidence ($H = 19.00$, $p = 0.000273$). It suggests that although the groups were all classified as "Confident" according to the Likert-scale interpretation, their confidence levels were not statistically comparable. For example, Class 3 had the highest AWM (3.66) and Class 4 had the lowest (3.41). Both classes were in the same verbal category, but their rankings and effects differed significantly.

Similarly, after code-switching was implemented, English grades improved in all classes, but the amount of improvement varied. Class 4 showed a comparatively modest gain (from 85 to 88), whereas Class 3 showed a significant increase (from 91 to 95). According to these findings, code-switching may not be equally effective for every learner, despite its general effectiveness. Contextual, instructional, or learner-specific factors may cause this variation.

The results back up what Algharabali et al. (2015) and Mauliddiyah et al. (2020) said: code-switching is a good way to help students understand and feel more confident about learning a new language. However, Gamotin (2021) and Masna (2020) stressed that depending on the students' background and level of proficiency in the two languages being used, their responses to code-switching can vary significantly. It also explains why the classes in this study showed statistically significant differences in academic performance and confidence levels.

Furthermore, Brice (2000) and Almagableh & Yunus (2022) stress the importance of equitable pedagogical practices when implementing code-switching in ESL classes. Teachers must remember that students' prior knowledge, engagement levels, and classroom settings affect these tactics. The Kruskal-Wallis test's statistical results show minor variations requiring attention through differentiated instruction and additional research, despite the general trend that code-switching improves grades and confidence.

The researcher's initial conclusion that all students were "confident" and benefited equally from

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code-switching needs to be qualified in light of these findings. Given the statistically significant difference, a more complex and unique explanation of how students comprehend and behave in code-switching scenarios is required. Ensuring that the benefits of code-switching are distributed equitably among all learner groups necessitates providing focused support and possibly tailored instructional strategies.

Following code-switching, some respondents reported feeling more confident. The result supports Ulfah et al.'s (2021) theory that translanguaging, or intentional code-switching, can empower students by utilizing their full linguistic repertoire, increasing their self-confidence and engagement in the classroom. It makes it easier for the students to be understood, especially in complex conversations or public speaking activities.

Table 3. Thematic Coding and Sample Responses

Theme	Sample Responses
1. Improved Confidence in English Communication	"I am now confident in speaking English" "I am now active in class discussion" "I am glad that I could speak fluent English by using code-switching" "Always ready to make my reporting in English"
2. Facilitates Grammar and Comprehension	"Code-switching helps me in understanding difficult grammar" "It improves my grammar" "My teacher helps me understand our discussion in English" "What I do is to memorize the line in English, then make a code-switching to comprehend the sentence"
3. Ongoing Struggle with Full English Use	"I am still slightly not confident with my English" "I am not yet ready to have our reporting in full English" "Not yet ready"

Students stated that code-switching simplified the understanding of the lesson content and helped them grasp grammar rules. Maulidiyah et al. (2020) and Rustiyani (2020) also pointed out that the utilization of L1 (mother tongue) can serve as a scaffold to comprehend L2 (target language) grammar and content, thus facilitating the learning process, particularly during early or middle stages of L2 acquisition.

The full use of English still causes anxiety in some students, especially in high-stakes situations like reporting. Hence, it supports the notion that code-switching would reduce anxiety, but excessive reliance may impede the growth of L2 fluency (Almagableh & Yunus, 2022).

Conclusions

This study aimed to find out how students think, feel, and act when switching between languages in English classes and how it affects their understanding, communication ability, and emotional involvement. According to the findings, code-switching greatly improved students' self-assurance, engagement, and comprehension of challenging grammatical explanations. Thematic analysis of student responses confirmed that code-switching is a valuable technique that helps close meaning gaps and promotes linguistic comfort.

The Kruskal-Wallis H test showed statistically significant differences between the class groups regarding self-perceived confidence and performance in English grades. Code-switching helps people learn, but how well it works depends on the situation. Not every student benefited in the same way, which emphasizes the necessity of differentiated instruction and teachers' awareness of student diversity. These findings result in the rejected null hypothesis, validating that code-switching significantly influences learners' cognitive and affective gains in English language learning.

In summary, code-switching is a teaching tool rather than a sign of a language deficit when employed effectively. It gives students a sense of control, improves comprehension, and increases their involvement in class, making it particularly helpful during the transitional stages of second language acquisition.

Implications for Practice

This study's results greatly affect how teachers teach, especially in classrooms where students speak more than one language. Code-switching can be a helpful way to teach if you use it carefully and with a purpose. It can help students understand and stay motivated. Teachers should use code-switching as a teaching tool, especially when working with complex vocabulary, abstract ideas, or grammar rules. It makes it easier for students to change their thinking and understand things better because it lets them connect what they are learning in a new language to what they already know about language.

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Furthermore, code-switching is a key component of creating an inclusive learning environment. Students can participate more confidently in class discussions and academic activities because code-switching validates and respects their linguistic and cultural identities. Students are more likely to participate, take intellectual risks, and express themselves sincerely in linguistically safe classrooms. As a result, code-switching can foster a cooperative, compassionate, and equitable classroom culture.

Teachers need enough training and professional development to use code-switching well. They need to know when and how to use code-switching, but they also need to know how to avoid using it too much, which could make it harder for students to learn the target language fully. Training sessions must help teachers align their methods with learning objectives and student proficiency levels while guiding the balanced use of code-switching.

Another important factor to consider is differentiated instruction. Teachers must assess each student's unique linguistic needs and modify their teaching strategies accordingly, as not all students equally share the benefits of code-switching. Code-switching will be an essential scaffold for some students but will not be as important for others. If these differences are acknowledged and addressed, instruction will remain effective and responsive for diverse learners.

Finally, incorporating code-switching and translanguaging into language education models would benefit curriculum developers and school principals. By acknowledging the practical realities of multilingual classrooms and confirming the validity of bilingual practice, curricula can be developed to empower students, enhance language learning, and promote academic success and linguistic self-confidence. Lastly, to address these implications, language pedagogy must be redesigned from rigid monolingual standards to more adaptable, contextually sensitive, and flexible methods that reflect students' changing linguistic lives.

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